

MODELLING RESIDUAL STRESSES IN THICK-SECTION THERMOPLASTIC COMPOSITES FOR WIND AND TIDAL ENERGY BLADES

Anastasia P. Tsavea¹, James Maguire¹, Colin Robert², Edward McCarthy³, Eduardo Barocio⁴,

R. Byron Pipes⁴, Conchúr M. Ó Brádaigh²

¹ School of Mechanical, Aerospace, and Civil Engineering, University of Sheffield, Mapping Street, Sheffield S1 3JD, UK

² School of Chemical, Materials, and Biological Engineering, University of Sheffield, Sir Robert Hadfield Building, Mappin Street, Sheffield S1 3JD, UK

³ School of Engineering, Institute for Materials and Processes, The University of Edinburgh, Sanderson Building, Robert Stevenson Road, Edinburgh EH9 3FB, Scotland, UK

⁴ Composites Manufacturing and Simulation Center, Purdue University, West Lafayette 47906, IN, United States

Keywords: Elium® thermoplastic composites, Process-induced residual stresses, CHILE model

ABSTRACT

The adoption of Elium® acrylic thermoplastic composites in wind energy and marine applications offers significant sustainability advantages through end-of-life recyclability. Process-induced residual stresses during room-temperature polymerisation remain a critical manufacturing challenge, however, with large through-thickness temperature gradients developing during processing of thick-section composites. While viscoelastic models can predict these stresses, they require extensive material characterisation that is particularly challenging for the rapidly-evolving properties of room-temperature reactive thermoplastics. This paper presents the application of the Cure Hardening Instantaneously Linear Elastic (CHILE) model to reactive thermoplastic composites, offering computational efficiency without sacrificing accuracy. The CHILE framework is implemented through coupled thermal-chemical-mechanical finite element analysis in ABAQUS, incorporating autocatalytic polymerisation kinetics, conversion-dependent material properties and a critical gelation criterion ($\alpha = 0.4$) that governs the transition from liquid to solid behaviour. Simulations of thick UD E-glass/Elium® laminates demonstrate the model's capability to predict temperature profiles, through-thickness gradients, and resulting thermal and chemical residual stress distributions. Comparative analysis of forced convection at an elevated temperature (30°C) reveals that elevated-temperature processing can reduce spring-back by 33% and peak tensile stresses by up to 65%, despite fundamentally reversing the warpage mode from U-shape to Ω -shape through altered thermal-chemical shrinkage coupling during polymerisation. These findings provide manufacturers with an efficient tool for process optimisation and establish a framework for sustainable composite manufacturing. Future work will explore adaptive temperature control strategies to minimise residual stress formation, and a quantitative comparison of stress calculations using CHILE and full viscoelastic formulations.

1 INTRODUCTION

The International Energy Agency's Renewables 2024 Outlook [1] projects that the world will install more than 5.5 TW of new renewable power between 2024 and 2030, propelled by a doubling of annual wind-capacity additions. This will raise the amount of electricity from clean sources to about 46% of global electricity by the decade's end. Wind and marine renewable energy systems are positioned to play a critical role in this transition, requiring robust infrastructure capable of withstanding harsh operational environments for 20-25 year service lives [2]. The sustainability of these technologies remains limited, however, by the predominance of thermoset composite materials, which are difficult to recycle at end-of-life and contribute to growing composite waste streams, estimated at 62,000 tonnes annually, predominantly arising from wind turbines blades [3].

Elium® resin, a liquid methyl methacrylate infusible thermoplastic, offers a transformative solution by enabling room-temperature processing with the recyclability advantages of thermoplastics [4]. This resin system has been successfully demonstrated in full-scale renewable energy applications, including the TIGER project's 18-meter tidal turbine blades and the ZEBRA project's 62-meter recyclable wind turbine blade manufactured by Arkema and LM Wind Power [5], seen in Figure 1. These demonstrators have validated Elium®'s mechanical performance while highlighting manufacturing challenges that must be addressed for widespread adoption.

Figure 1 The world's then-largest recyclable Elium® wind blade, constructed as part of the ZEBRA project in 2022 – it has since been surpassed in length by a 77-metre blade manufactured by the same consortium [5].

Wind and tidal-turbine blades are designed to survive up to 10^8 – 10^9 variable-amplitude fatigue cycles over a 20-year life (IEC 61400-5), and recent full-scale tests at the University of Edinburgh's FastBlade facility confirm that tidal energy blades experience highly complex cyclic loads, enduring an entire lifetime's loading when exercised at 18–20 Hz for an equivalent 20 years [6]. Process-induced residual stresses significantly impact fatigue performance by superimposing on service loads, essentially acting as an internal mean load that accelerates fatigue damage in composites [7]. On wind-blade-grade glass/epoxy laminates, lowering residual stresses by 50 % triples the cycles to failure, while a 75% reduction extends life by roughly an order of magnitude, confirming residual-stress magnitude as a dominant lever in composite fatigue durability [8].

In reactive thermoplastic systems like Elium®, residual stresses arise from two coupled mechanisms during polymerisation. Chemical shrinkage, which in the case of Elium® is reported to result in a 13% volumetric reduction, according to Bamane et al. [9], occurs as polymer chains form and densify. Simultaneously, the exothermic polymerisation reaction generates temperature rises of up to 100°C in thick sections. This leads to thermal stresses due to global temperature gradients, as well as thermal expansion coefficient mismatches between the matrix and fibre phases [10]. The interaction between these mechanisms, combined with the material's transition from liquid to solid state during polymerisation, creates complex stress fields that vary significantly through component thickness.

Skin-core residual-stress and temperature gradients are a hallmark of thick composite laminates. Bogetti and Gillespie showed that the complex stress gradients which arise are sensitive to various factors including resin properties, laminate thickness, and processing history [13]. They showed that in cases where outside-to-inside curing arises, the laminate skins can be locked into compression while the solidifying core is put in tension; with the resulting stresses being sufficient to induce transverse cracking in some cases. In terms of wind and tidal turbine blades, Maguire et al. simulated the oven-curing of thick blade sections and showed that the use of low-exotherm resins and modified processing cycles can reduce thermal and cure gradients during critical periods (e.g. during gelation) [11]. In Elium® parts the exotherm peaks at the mid-plane [12], so polymerisation typically proceeds inside-out; the core

contracts first and is later restrained by the belatedly polymerised skins, giving the opposite stress sign (tensile centre, compressive outer plies). This effect creates a need for tailored polymerisation and temperature profiles to avoid warpage and residual-stress build-up.

Three primary modelling approaches exist for predicting process-induced residual stresses. Linear elastic models, while computationally efficient, cannot capture the evolving material state during polymerisation. Viscoelastic models provide the highest fidelity by tracking the complete stress history through polymerisation, as demonstrated in the seminal works of Bogetti and Gillespie [13] and White and Hahn [14]. However, the Cure Hardening Instantaneously Linear Elastic (CHILE) approach, introduced by Johnston et al. [15], has become widely adopted in process modelling of composites as it offers a compromise by assuming instantaneously elastic behaviour only after gelation while maintaining computational efficiency. While CHILE models typically overestimate residual stresses because they neglect matrix stress-relaxation [16], they provide a conservative, worst-case assessment that serves as an acceptable first-order approximation of material behaviour.

The application of viscoelastic models to Elium® composites faces unique challenges. Unlike high-temperature epoxy systems where reactions can be arrested by cooling, Elium® polymerises at room temperature, making it impossible to "freeze" intermediate conversion states for property characterisation. The rapid evolution from low-viscosity liquid ($\mu = 0.1 \text{ Pa}\cdot\text{s}$) to solid polymer ($E = 3.2 \text{ GPa}$) occurs within hours, requiring extensive time-dependent testing that is both technically challenging and computationally intensive to implement. With respect to the latter, full viscoelastic analyses typically require 20-50 times more computational resources than equivalent CHILE/pseudo-viscoelastic simulations, while offering moderate accuracy improvements for final residual stress predictions ([17], [18]). Nonetheless, no such comparative studies have been produced yet for Elium® room-temperature processing resins in particular, as of the current time of writing of this paper.

This paper presents the implementation of a CHILE framework specifically adapted for reactive thermoplastic composites, as a step towards addressing the critical need for efficient residual stress management in sustainable composite manufacturing. By capturing the essential physics of polymerisation-induced stresses while maintaining computational tractability, this approach enables practical process optimisation for next-generation recyclable composite structures.

2 CHILE MODEL FORMULATION AND THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

The Cure Hardening Instantaneously Linear Elastic (CHILE) model offers a computationally efficient framework for predicting process-induced residual stresses while capturing the essential physics of polymerisation. The key distinction from viscoelastic models is that CHILE assumes the material responds purely elastically to each strain increment after gelation, using only the instantaneous modulus at the current conversion state. In contrast, viscoelastic models account for the entire loading history through hereditary integrals, where stresses depend on when strains were applied relative to the evolving relaxation modulus. The CHILE framework decomposes the total strain increment into three components:

$$d\varepsilon_{ij}^{\text{total}} = d\varepsilon_{ij}^{\text{elastic}} + d\varepsilon_{ij}^{\text{thermal}} + d\varepsilon_{ij}^{\text{chemical}} \quad (1)$$

where the thermal and chemical strains evolve continuously throughout polymerisation according to:

$$d\varepsilon^{\text{thermal}} = \alpha_{\text{CTE}}(T, \alpha) \cdot dT \quad (2)$$

$$d\varepsilon^{\text{chemical}} = \beta_{\text{CS}} \cdot d\alpha \quad (3)$$

Here, α represents the degree of conversion ($0 \leq \alpha \leq 1$), α_{CTE} is the coefficient of thermal expansion, and β_{CS} is the chemical shrinkage coefficient. The polymerisation kinetics follow an autocatalytic model with diffusion control:

$$\frac{d\alpha}{dt} = (k_1 + k_2\alpha^m)(1 - \alpha)^n \cdot f_d(\alpha, T) \quad (4)$$

where k_1 and k_2 are temperature-dependent rate constants following Arrhenius relationships, m and n are reaction exponents, and $f_d(\alpha, T)$ represents diffusion limitations at high conversion, and is dependent on the degree of conversion and the temperature.

A critical aspect of CHILE residual stress calculation models is the gelation criterion. As liquid resin cannot sustain mechanical stress, the material accommodates all thermal and chemical strains through viscous flow prior to gelation. After the physical-gel point, these accumulated strains instantaneously generate elastic stresses based on the evolving stiffness tensor $C_{ijkl}(\alpha)$. The stiffness matrix is constructed using a given fibre-volume fraction and micromechanics, based on the evolving tensile modulus E (Figure 2), shear modulus G and Poisson's ratio ν of the resin. In the case of Elium® 191 XO/SA, where $\alpha_{gel} \approx 0.4$ [9], the following holds true:

$$\sigma_{ij} = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{if } \alpha < 0.4 \\ C_{ijkl}(\alpha) \cdot \varepsilon_{ij}^{elastic} & \text{if } \alpha \geq 0.4 \end{cases} \quad (5)$$

The CHILE model assumes that: (i) the material behaves as a nearly incompressible liquid before gelation, (ii) the transition to solid behaviour occurs instantaneously at the gel point (an approximation of this assumption was used for numerical stability), (iii) smooth transition to post-gelation behaviour is linear elastic with polymerisation-dependent properties, and (iv) no stress relaxation occurs after gelation. These assumptions, while simplifying the complex viscoelastic behaviour of polymerising systems, capture the dominant mechanisms of residual stress formation.

Figure 2 Evolution of resin's Young's Modulus in the CHILE formulation

3 NUMERICAL IMPLEMENTATION AND MATERIAL MODELLING

3.1 ABAQUS/Standard FEA simulation

The coupled thermal-chemical-mechanical analysis was implemented in ABAQUS/Standard using user-defined subroutines to capture the thermo-chemo-mechanical behaviour of Elium® polymerisation. The finite element model employs C3D8T coupled temperature-displacement elements, which provide simultaneous solution of heat transfer and mechanical equilibrium equations essential for capturing

process-induced residual stresses. The laminate geometry (200 mm by 200 mm, with an equivalent thickness of 60 plies, or 52.95 mm) was discretised with a structured mesh refined through the thickness. The mesh consists of over 70,000 nodes and 65,000 elements. The mesh was determined to be sufficient in calculating accurate residual stress and deformation results for this simulation. A two-step approach was used to reflect the polymerisation/consolidation phase, and the instantaneous tool-removal stage. Step 1 simulated the 24-hour polymerisation using coupled temperature-displacement analysis with automatic time incrementation (initial = 100s, minimum = 0.05s, maximum = 200s). The maximum temperature change per increment was limited to 2°C to ensure accurate capture of the exothermic peak. Step 2 modelled the tool removal as a static step, releasing the substrate constraint to reveal final part distortion.

The bottom surface (substrate interface) was constrained in the through-thickness z-direction to prevent rigid body motion while allowing in-plane deformation during the consolidation phase on a one-sided tool. Three reference nodes were constrained to prevent numerical singularities: a central node fixed in all directions, a second node constrained in x and z, and a third node constrained only in z-direction. These three nodes remain active in the second step of tool removal to permit free warpage of the laminate while still suppressing rigid-body modes, thereby capturing the true redistribution of residual stresses without numerical drift. Thermal boundary conditions specified natural convective heat transfer ($h = 10 \text{ W/m}^2 \cdot \text{K}$) on the top surface with remaining surfaces insulated, representing typical open-mould processing. At this point, no thermal resistances have been implemented to represent the thermal effect of the tool (heat sink), in order to produce a first-order assessment of residual stress formation.

Four main ABAQUS user subroutines implemented the CHILE framework. USDFLD solved the autocatalytic kinetics using fourth-order Runge-Kutta integration, updating the degree of conversion field variable. HETVAL calculated internal heat generation from the polymerisation rate and heat of reaction. UEXPAN defined thermal and chemical strain increments based on composite micromechanics. UMAT implemented the gelation-dependent stiffness matrix, transitioning from liquid ($E = 1 \text{ kPa}$) to the commencement of solid-like behaviour at $\alpha = 0.40$. A flowchart overview of the model can be found in Figure 3.

Figure 3 CHILE residual stress numerical scheme flowchart – key interactions.

Numerical stability was ensured through multiple strategies, including clamping degree of conversion between 0 and 0.999999, implementing overflow protection in exponential calculations, and checking for near-singular stiffness matrices.

3.2 Elium® 191 XO/SA Material Model

Elium® material properties were derived from resin molecular dynamics simulations by Bamane et al. [9]. The autocatalytic polymerisation kinetics were derived from best-fit DSC curves and incorporate both chemical reaction and diffusion limitations, seen in Table 1.

Table 1 Polymerisation kinetics.

Property	Symbol	Value	Unit
Fibre volume fraction	V_f	0.52	–
Heat of reaction	ΔH	253	kJ/kg
Pre-exponential factor 1	A_1	4.18	1/s
Pre-exponential factor 2	A_2	2.42×10^5	1/s
Activation energy 1	E_1	26.5	kJ/mol
Activation energy 2	E_2	41.8	kJ/mol
Autocatalytic exponent	m	2.86	–
Diffusion exponent	n	2.02	–
Gelation point	α_{gel}	0.40	–

Composite properties were calculated using micromechanics, with equivalent chemical shrinkage of -0.19% longitudinal strain and -0.37% transverse strain, reflecting fibre constraint effects, and equivalent coefficients of thermal expansion of $6.1 \times 10^{-6} \text{ K}^{-1}$ in the fibre direction and $25 \times 10^{-6} \text{ K}^{-1}$ in both transverse directions.

4 NUMERICAL RESULTS

4.1 Thick Laminate Case Study 1: Unidirectional Laminate

The through-thickness thermal profile of the laminate (Figure 4) shows lower temperature change ΔT from ambient (20°C) at the top surface, which is closest to the convective boundary. On the contrary, the bottom of the laminate reaches the highest temperature from ambient (82°C), as it is located furthest away from the convective boundary, resulting in through-thickness thermal gradients of approximately 30°C .

Figure 4 Left: Schematic of mesh and laminate location definitions. Right: Relative temperature increase from ambient 20°C , at the centre of a 52.95mm GF/Elium® laminate.

Similarly, the degrees of conversion were tracked, with a slight lag in the polymerisation of the top of the laminate being observed as a result of the convective heat loss boundary condition (Figure 5).

Figure 5 Through-thickness degrees of conversion at the centre of the laminate.

Following the removal of the tool, the unidirectional laminate experiences cylindrical bending as a result of the thermal and chemical stresses that developed during polymerisation. Displacement results are shown in metres in Figure 6. Owing to its omission of viscoelastic relaxation, the CHILE formulation would typically overpredict the deformation observed experimentally.

Figure 6 Cylindrical warpage of the 60-ply unidirectional GF/Elium® unidirectional laminate.

Chemical and thermal strains were also tracked (Figure 7), with results shown for the 1-direction - along the fibres. The maximum chemical strain (-0.00191) significantly dominates the maximum thermal strain (0.00038), showing that residual stress formation in the case of Elium® is a phenomenon largely driven by chemical shrinkage, and additionally due to the low temperature increase of the laminate from ambient (approximately 60°C relative temperature increase).

Figure 7 Thermal (left) and chemical (right) Strains during consolidation stage.

While strains occur from the beginning of the polymerisation, stresses do not become locked-in prior to gelation. Once the gelation condition is triggered ($\alpha = 0.4$), chemical strains initially cause compression and subsequently the rate of thermal expansion surpasses the rate of chemical shrinkage, resulting in a bounce-back effect. Subsequently, as the exothermic reaction accelerates, and the rate of conversion increases, therefore resulting in a rapid increase of chemical stress. Afterwards, the laminate enters a cool-down phase, during which chemical stresses remain compressive, but in addition, thermal stresses become compressive as well ($\Delta T < 0$).

The fibre-direction stress (S11) evolution (Figure 8) during the polymerisation process exhibits significant spatial variation and magnitude differences across the composite laminate. At the geometric centre (left), substantial residual stresses develop, with the top layer reaching approximately 12.5 MPa of tensile stress, and the bottom layer developing compressive stresses of -5 MPa, while the middle layer remains at a much lower compressive stress state. This through-thickness gradient indicates significant bending moments induced by polymerisation shrinkage and thermal effects, and specifically the sequential polymerisation process: the middle and bottom layers polymerise and shrink first, then act as rigid constraints preventing the top layer from freely shrinking during its later polymerisation, forcing it into tension while the bottom layer experiences compression from the tool constraint. As seen later in section 4.3, upon tool removal, this asymmetric stress distribution creates a bending moment that causes the part to warp and the stress states to invert, with the previously compressed bottom surface transitioning to tension and the top surface stress transitioning to compression.

The corner region (right) demonstrates more complex transient behaviour, with the middle and bottom layers initially developing tensile stresses up to 0.12 MPa, followed by an asymptotic stress equilibrium toward 0.05MPa, while the top layer momentarily oscillates between tensile and compressive stresses before remaining at a very small compressive state throughout the end of consolidation. The marked difference in stress magnitudes between centre (± 2.5 -12.5 MPa) and corner (± 0.12 MPa) locations reveals that the centre experiences substantially higher residual stresses, likely due to greater constraint from surrounding material, whereas the corner's proximity to free edges allows for stress relief through deformation.

Figure 8 S11 stresses during consolidation stage at the centre (left) and a corner (right) of the laminate - stresses remain at zero pre-gelation as prescribed.

4.2 Thick Laminate Case Study 2: Elevated Temperature

To model the effect of oven heating at 30°C, an additional subroutine was employed to impose a forced convection to the top surface during the temperature rise in the centre of the laminate due to the exotherm. The aim was to gain further insight into residual stress mitigation strategies by reducing the skin-core effect present in Elium® laminates, where the core polymerises first due to heat not dissipating as effectively as the surfaces exposed to convection, therefore initiating premature shrinkage of the core earlier than the edges. The main differences implemented in the simulation are (a) longer consolidation time at room temperature following the forced convection phase, to allow for full cool-down prior to tool removal and (b) a supplementary FILM subroutine whereby the laminate top surface is exposed to forced convection condition with $h = 30 \text{ W/m}^2 \cdot \text{K}$ at a pre-heated oven with a temperature of 30°C.

This heated condition is implemented until the temperature at centre of the laminate peaks (to promote concurrent polymerisation initiation at the middle and top of the laminate) and instantaneously removed and replaced by the natural convection at ambient temperature previously discussed.

The implementation of elevated temperature processing with controlled forced convection demonstrated significant mitigation of the skin-core thermal gradient characteristic of thick GF/Elium® laminate polymerisation, as seen in Figure 9. Application of 30°C forced convection until peak exotherm, followed by natural convection cooling, essentially broadens (resulting in a slight bimodality due to lagged heat transfer from inner-layer exotherm) and lowers the temperature profile at the top of the laminate (top). The result is higher through-thickness temperature gradients compare to the ambient case study. Nevertheless, the modified thermal profile promoted synchronised polymerisation initiation across the laminate thickness (bottom left), significantly reducing the temporal conversion gradient observed under ambient conditions (bottom right).

Figure 9 Comparison of ambient and elevated temperature processing case studies in terms of (top) temperature, (bottom left) degree of conversion, and (bottom right) skin-core temporal difference in degree of conversion.

4.3 Comparison of Case Studies: Post Tool-Removal

Following tool removal in both cases, the addition of forced convection fundamentally altered the residual stress state, manifesting as an inversion of the warpage mode from concave (U-shaped) to convex (Ω -shaped) curvature. The individual through-thickness stress states can be found in Figure 10. In absolute terms, there are reductions in final stresses in σ_{11} , σ_{22} , and σ_{23} , while σ_{33} and σ_{13} have remained essentially constant. A comparative summary of the worst-cases across all locations (centre and edges) of key parameters can be found in Table 2.

Investigating the edge effects, it becomes clear that there is significantly higher in-plane difference in the elevated temperature case, where the edge-to-centre stress ratio surpasses 500 for τ_{23} , as seen in Figure 11. This extreme stress concentration at edges in the elevated temperature case likely results from the more severe thermal gradients creating differential shrinkage patterns that are accommodated through interlaminar shear at the free boundaries, where the absence of constraint allows stress singularities to develop more prominently than in the room temperature case.

Figure 10 Through-thickness worst-cases stress states in ambient (top row) and forced convection (bottom row) cases.

Figure 11 Summary of edge/centre stress ratios for room temperature (left) and elevated temperature (right) cases.

As seen in Table 2, the elevated temperature processing strategy achieved a 33% reduction in spring-back displacement (13.4 mm to 9.0 mm) despite generating 4.7% higher peak temperatures during the exothermic polymerisation of the thick UD Elium® laminate. Additionally, the fibre-direction stress (σ_{11}) range (maximum tensile stress minus maximum compressive stress) reduced from 38.2 MPa to 21.3 MPa with a 65% reduction in peak tension (25.8MPa reduced to 9MPa), and the through-thickness normal stress (σ_{33}) shifted from predominantly tensile (+1.06 MPa) to compressive (-0.81 MPa). The transverse stress (σ_{22}) demonstrated a significant reduction, with the stress range decreasing from 2.1 MPa (room temperature) to 0.3 MPa (elevated temperature), representing an 86% reduction driven primarily by a 93% decrease in peak tensile stress (1.5 MPa to 0.1 MPa) while compressive stresses remained minimal in both cases. The interlaminar shear stress τ_{23} showed a 40% reduction, indicating improved mitigation of edge effects, while maintaining similar compressive stress magnitudes in both cases (~12.4 MPa). Despite these improvements, the 9.0 mm residual warpage in the elevated

temperature case still represents unacceptable dimensional instability for practical applications. Nonetheless, these findings indicate that relatively modest thermal control interventions during the polymerisation phase can substantially influence the development of manufacturing-induced residual stresses in thick thermoplastic structures.

Table 2 Summary of key comparative results between worst-case room temperature and elevated temperature processing, across all locations (centre and edges).

Parameter	Room Temperature (20°C)	Elevated Temperature (30°C)	Change (%)
Peak Temperature (°C)	83.1	87.0	+4.7
Final σ_{11} Compression (MPa)	-12.4	-12.3	-0.8
Final σ_{11} Tension (MPa)	25.8	9.0	-65.1
Final σ_{22} Compression (MPa)	-0.6	-0.2	-66.7
Final σ_{22} Tension (MPa)	1.5	0.1	-93.3
Final σ_{33} Compression (MPa)	-0.13	-0.81	+523.1
Final σ_{33} Tension (MPa)	1.06	0.02	-98.1
Final τ_{13} Shear (MPa)	0.625	0.601	-3.8
Final τ_{23} Shear (MPa)	0.242	0.145	-40.1
Max Spring-back (mm)	13.4	9.0	-32.8
Final Curvature Direction	U-shape (bottom tension)	Ω -shape (bottom compression)	—

5 CONCLUSIONS

This study demonstrated the application of the CHILE framework for predicting process-induced residual stresses in thick Elium® thermoplastic composites, providing manufacturers with a computationally efficient tool for process optimisation. The model captures the coupling between exothermic polymerisation, chemical shrinkage, and mechanical response, revealing that chemical shrinkage dominates thermal effects in driving residual stress formation. Comparative analysis of ambient versus elevated temperature processing revealed that modest thermal interventions can achieve 33% spring-back reduction and 65% decrease in peak tensile stresses, though the resulting 9 mm warpage remains unacceptable for industrial applications. Critically, the complete reversal of the warpage mode (U-shape to Ω -shape) demonstrates the extreme process sensitivity of thick unidirectional laminates, highlighting fundamental manufacturability challenges that cannot be overcome through process optimisation alone. The dramatic edge stress concentrations, particularly the 500-fold increase in τ_{23} for elevated temperature processing, underscore the three-dimensional nature of residual stress development in thick sections to reduce risk of delamination. As CHILE inherently overestimates residual stresses by neglecting viscoelastic relaxation, future implementation of full viscoelastic models may reveal lower stress magnitudes and reduced warpage predictions. Nevertheless, the severe dimensional instability and edge effects observed even in these conservative estimates suggest that achieving manufacturability in thick Elium® wind and tidal energy structures will require careful consideration of both layup architecture and processing strategies.

REFERENCES

- [1] ‘Renewables 2024 – Analysis’, IEA. Accessed: Jun. 06, 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://www.iea.org/reports/renewables-2024>
- [2] S. M. Woo and J. Whale, ‘A mini-review of end-of-life management of wind turbines: Current practices and closing the circular economy gap’, *Waste Manag. Res.*, vol. 40, no. 12, pp. 1730–1744, Dec. 2022, doi: 10.1177/0734242X221105434.

- [3] A. Isa, N. Nosbi, M. Che Ismail, H. Md Akil, W. F. F. Wan Ali, and M. F. Omar, 'A Review on Recycling of Carbon Fibres: Methods to Reinforce and Expected Fibre Composite Degradations', *Materials*, vol. 15, no. 14, p. 4991, Jul. 2022, doi: 10.3390/ma15144991.
- [4] M. L. Devine, 'Liquid acrylic resin-based composites for marine and renewable energy applications', PhD Dissertation, School of Engineering, The University of Edinburgh, Scotland, UK, 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://era.ed.ac.uk/handle/1842/43530>
- [5] IRT Jules Verne, 'Breakthrough in Wind Turbine Blade Recycling: ZEBRA Project Demonstrates Closed-Loop System', Press release, Oct. 2024. [Online]. Available: https://www.arkema.com/files/live/sites/shared_arkema/files/downloads/news-attachments/global/en/press-release/2024/20241003_Press%20release%20Arkema%20Zebra.pdf
- [6] S. Lopez Dubon, C. Vogel, D. Garcia Cava, F. Cuthill, E. D. McCarthy, and C. M. Ó Brádaigh, 'A Full-Scale Tidal Blade Fatigue Test using the FastBlade Facility', *Renew. Energy*, vol. 228, p. 120653, Jul. 2024, doi: 10.1016/j.renene.2024.120653.
- [7] J. Hüther and P. Brøndsted, 'Influence of the curing cycles on the fatigue performance of unidirectional glass fiber reinforced epoxy composites: 37th Risø International Symposium on Materials Science', *O P Conf. Ser. Mater. Sci. Eng.*, vol. 139, 2016, doi: 10.1088/1757-899X/139/1/012023.
- [8] M. A. Miranda Maduro, *Influence of Curing Cycle on the Build-up of Residual Stresses and the Effect on the Mechanical Performance of Fibre Composites*. Risø, Roskilde, Denmark: DTU Wind Energy, 2021.
- [9] S. S. Bamane, P. P. Deshpande, S. U. Patil, M. Maiaru, and G. M. Odegard, 'Evolution of Physical, Thermal, and Mechanical Properties of Poly(methyl Methacrylate)-Based Elium Thermoplastic Polymer During Polymerization', *J. Phys. Chem. C*, vol. 128, no. 37, pp. 15639–15648, Sep. 2024, doi: 10.1021/acs.jpcc.4c04061.
- [10] P. P. Parlevliet, H. E. N. Bersee, and A. Beukers, 'Residual stresses in thermoplastic composites—A study of the literature—Part I: Formation of residual stresses', *Compos. Part Appl. Sci. Manuf.*, vol. 37, no. 11, pp. 1847–1857, Nov. 2006, doi: 10.1016/j.compositesa.2005.12.025.
- [11] J. M. Maguire, N. D. Sharp, R. B. Pipes, and C. M. Ó Brádaigh, 'Advanced process simulations for thick-section epoxy powder composite structures', *Compos. Part Appl. Sci. Manuf.*, vol. 161, p. 107073, Oct. 2022, doi: 10.1016/j.compositesa.2022.107073.
- [12] S. F. Gayot, C. Bailly, T. Pardoën, P. Gérard, and F. Van Loock, 'Processing maps based on polymerization modelling of thick methacrylic laminates', *Mater. Des.*, vol. 196, p. 109170, Nov. 2020, doi: 10.1016/j.matdes.2020.109170.
- [13] T. A. Bogetti and J. W. Gillespie Jr, 'Process-Induced Stress and Deformation in Thick-Section Thermoset Composite Laminates', *J. Compos. Mater.*, vol. 26, no. 5, pp. 626–660, Mar. 1992, doi: 10.1177/002199839202600502.
- [14] S. R. White and H. T. Hahn, 'Cure Cycle Optimization for the Reduction of Processing-Induced Residual Stresses in Composite Materials', *J. Compos. Mater.*, vol. 27, no. 14, pp. 1352–1378, Dec. 1993, doi: 10.1177/002199839302701402.
- [15] A. Johnston, R. Vaziri, and A. Poursartip, 'A Plane Strain Model for Process-Induced Deformation of Laminated Composite Structures', *J. Compos. Mater.*, vol. 35, no. 16, pp. 1435–1469, Aug. 2001, doi: 10.1106/YXEA-5MH9-76J5-BACK.
- [16] W. Chen and D. Zhang, 'Improved prediction of residual stress induced warpage in thermoset composites using a multiscale thermo-viscoelastic processing model', *Compos. Part Appl. Sci. Manuf.*, vol. 126, p. 105575, Nov. 2019, doi: 10.1016/j.compositesa.2019.105575.
- [17] M. Sandberg, O. Yuksel, I. Baran, J. Spangenberg, and J. H. Hattel, 'Steady-state modelling and analysis of process-induced stress and deformation in thermoset pultrusion processes', *Compos. Part B Eng.*, vol. 216, p. 108812, Jul. 2021, doi: 10.1016/j.compositesb.2021.108812.
- [18] J. Dai, S. Xi, and D. Li, 'Numerical Analysis of Curing Residual Stress and Deformation in Thermosetting Composite Laminates with Comparison between Different Constitutive Models', *Materials*, vol. 12, no. 4, Art. no. 4, Jan. 2019, doi: 10.3390/ma12040572.